

FORMATION OF ALUMINIUM *o*-CRESOTATE CHELATE: POTENTIOMETRIC AND CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES

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Increase in H^+ -concentration of monosodium *o*-cresotate has been observed on the addition of aluminium chloride solution. The increase in H^+ -concentration may be ascribed to the displacement of hydroxyl hydrogen in the complex formation. In the potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 mixtures of aluminium chloride and monosodium *o*-cresotate, the inflections and breaks at one equivalent of alkali indicate the formation of a complex containing aluminium and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio. The second inflection at three equivalents of alkali shows the precipitation of aluminium hydroxide.

Aluminium forms complexes with malic (Delsal, *J. chim. phys.*, 1938, 35, 350), tartaric (Spacu and Popper, *Kolloid Z.*, 1943, 103, 19) and salicylic acids (Burrows and Wark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 222) and with 2:3-dihydroxynaphthalene (Weinland and Seuffert, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1928, 283, 455). Moser *et al.* (*Monatsh.*, 1922, 43, 678) have shown that in presence of sulphosalicylic acid, aluminium is not precipitated as hydroxide. Aluminium salts of sulphosalicylic, sulphobenzoic and sulphohydroxynaphthoic acids have been prepared by Dominikiewicz (*Arch. Chem. Pharm.*, 1934, 1, 93). Salicylate complexes have been investigated in detail by Babko *et al.* (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1948, 18, 1617). In weakly acidic solutions, a complex $(Al\ Sal)^+$ is formed. With rise in p_H and the corresponding increase in the concentration of salicylate ions, a second and a third stage of the complex formation take place, consistent with the formation of $(Al\ Sal)_2^-$ and $(Al\ Sal)_3^{2-}$ successively. Illari (*Anal. Chim. Appl.*, 1952, 42, 32) obtained crystals of aluminium salicylate by refluxing aluminium nitrate and salicylic acid. Spectrophotometric study of the complex formation between aluminium and sulphosalicylic acid was carried out by Anderson and Lysater (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1429) and the formation of 1:1 complex up to p_H 5.0 was confirmed.

Singh (D. Phil. thesis, Allahabad Univ., 1956) has investigated 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of aluminium with sulphosalicylic and chloromercuri-sulphosalicylic acids by potentiometric and conductometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of aluminium chloride were made by dissolving Baker's analysed sample of $AlCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ in water and the aluminium content was estimated gravimetrically as $Al(C_6H_5ON)_3$ with 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) (Vogel, "Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1951, p. 372).

Monosodium salt of *o*-cresotic acid was prepared by the addition of an equivalent amount of an E. Merck-A.R. sample of sodium bicarbonate in a B.D.H.-L.R. sample of

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o-cresotic acid. The mother-liquor was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The crude sample of monosodium salt of *o*-cresotic acid was crystallised in absolute alcohol in white shining crystals and dried in a desiccator. Carbon, hydrogen and oxygen contents were determined by combustion. Standard solutions of monosodium *o*-cresotatate were prepared by direct weighing of the prepared sample.

All the measurements were made at a constant temperature of $32^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$; p_{H} was measured with a Leeds Northrup A.C.-operated p_{H} -meter using glass and saturated calomel electrodes. The instrument was standardised with a standard buffer solution.

Electrical conductivity was measured by a Leeds Northrup Kohlrausch slide wire bridge with an A. C. -operated audiodfrequency oscillator in the circuit. The null point was detected by the headphone supplied by the same manufacturers.

Complex-forming Systems.—To study the complex formation of aluminium with monosodium *o*-cresotatate, monovariant method was used. To constant volumes of aluminium chloride varying amounts of monosodium *o*-cresotatate were added. Thus, a number of sets of mixtures containing aluminium chloride and monosodium *o*-cresotatate in the ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 were prepared. To these mixtures varying amounts of standard solutions of caustic soda were added. The total volume of the mixtures was kept constant in each case. The sets were left for about 24 hours to attain the equilibrium. p_{H} and specific conductivity of the mixtures were measured at a constant temperature. For comparison, aluminium chloride and monosodium *o*-cresotatate were titrated separately with alkali by potentiometric and conductometric methods under similar conditions.

DISCUSSION

In the graphs, the number of equivalents of alkali is represented by abscissa while physical properties, viz., p_{H} and specific conductivity, by ordinate.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1 represents the changes in hydrogen-ion concentration in monosodium *o*-cresotatate (0.05 M) solution by the addition of varying amounts of aluminium chloride (0.05 M). The curve A shows that p_{H} of monosodium *o*-cresotatate (6.80) decreases by the addition of aluminium chloride. No major change is brought about in the p_{H} of the mixture after 3.1, when about one equivalent of aluminium chloride is added. Curve A' represents the p_{H} of aluminium chloride only at similar concentrations. As the curve A for the mixture lies below A', it is evident that there is an increase in hydrogen-ion concentration in the system, which is only possible by the displacement of hydroxyl hydrogen of *o*-cresotatate by aluminium. This shows that aluminium forms a complex with *o*-cresotatate; the reaction may be represented as:

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Fig. 2 shows the variation of hydrogen-ion concentration with the progressive addition of alkali to the systems: (i) aluminium chloride (0.10 *M*) (curve A) and mixtures of aluminium chloride (0.10 *M*) and monosodium *o*-cresotate (0.10 *M*) in the ratios of (ii) 1:1 (curve B), (iii) 1:2 (curve C), (iv) 1:3 (curve D) and (v) 1:4 (curve E), while the curve F shows the reaction of alkali on monosodium *o*-cresotate itself.

In curve A (Fig. 2), the precipitation of aluminium hydroxide started at about p_{H} 6.05 and was complete when three equivalents of alkali were added. At about p_{H} 10.5, when addition of four equivalents of alkali was complete, the precipitate of aluminium hydroxide dissolved, forming aluminate.

The reaction can be represented by the following equations:

From curve F (Fig. 2), it is clearly indicated that no liberation of hydroxyl hydrogen of monosodium *o*-cresotate takes place by alkali, and by the addition of only a little alkali there is a steep rise in p_{H} (7.30 to 11.20), showing no free hydrogen ion present in the system to be titrated by alkali.

When varying amounts of alkali were added in the mixtures (1:1-1:4) of 0.10 *M* aluminium chloride and 0.10 *M* monosodium *o*-cresotate, a small amount of a white precipitate appeared in the systems, but when the sets were left to attain the equilibrium, the precipitate formed was seen to dissolve up to about p_{H} 5.0, and above this p_{H} (5.0) a gelatinous white precipitate of aluminium hydroxide persisted (curves B, C, D, E, Fig. 2). The precipitation of aluminium hydroxide was completed by the addition of three equivalents of alkali, and the gelatinous white precipitate of aluminium hydroxide again dissolved after the addition of four equivalents of alkali, forming aluminate (equations ii and iii).

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

When the p_H is plotted against the equivalents of alkali, it is clear that there is one inflection in the curves B, C, D, E (Fig. 2) at one equivalent of alkali, showing the complete precipitation of aluminium hydroxide. The occurrence of first inflection can be explained by assuming that at about p_H 4.25, a complex is completely formed containing aluminium and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio. It can also be inferred from the curves that in the formation of the complex, the hydroxyl hydrogen of *o*-cresotate is displaced by aluminium and oxygen atoms of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups share in the complex formation. The reaction can be represented by equation (i).

The complex started breaking at about p_H 5.0, resulting in the precipitation of aluminium hydroxide, which was complete at about p_H 8.0.

Figs. 3 and 4 represent the results of p_H measurements in similar experiments, as in Fig. 2, with two lower concentrations (0.05 *M* and 0.025 *M*) of the reactants. The curves A, B, C, D, E and F of Figs. 3 and 4 are of exactly similar nature as curves A, B, C, D, E and F of Fig. 2 which provide sufficient evidence for the formation of complex of aluminium with *o*-cresotate, containing aluminium and *o*-cresotate in 1:1 ratio, in acidic medium.

Similar observations were made with the specific conductivity study (Fig. 5). The curve A (Fig. 5) shows the conductometric titration of aluminium chloride (0.10 *M*) with caustic soda. From the examination of the curve A (Fig. 5), it is seen that there is a definite break in the curves at about three equivalents of alkali, which shows

the complete precipitation of aluminium hydroxide. By the addition of four equivalents of alkali, the gelatinous precipitate of aluminium hydroxide dissolved completely, forming aluminate. The reaction can be represented by equations (i) and (ii).

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

The curves B, C, D and E (Fig. 5) represent the conductometric titration of (1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4) mixtures of aluminium chloride (0.1 *M*) and monosodium *o*-cresotatate (0.10 *M*) respectively by alkali. All the curves show only one break at one equivalent of alkali. This shows the formation of only one complex of aluminium and *o*-cresotatate containing the two reactants in 1:1 ratio. The reaction may be represented by equation (i).

In Figs. 6 and 7, the results of similar experiments, as in Fig. 5, with two lower concentrations (0.05 *M* and 0.025 *M*) of the reactants obtained by specific conductivity study are plotted graphically. All the curves, A, B, C, D and E of Figs. 6 and 7, give the same conclusion as shown by the curves of Fig. 5. It also shows the formation of only one complex containing aluminium and *o*-cresotatate in 1:1 ratio.

From the above observations of p_H and specific conductivity measurements (Figs. 1-7), it has become quite clear that aluminium forms only one complex with monosodium *o*-cresotatate in 1:1 ratio. In case of salicylic acid, Babko *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have shown the formation of three complexes with aluminium, but in the case of *o*-cresotatate there is indication of formation of only one complex. They have pointed

out that in weakly acidic solutions, aluminium forms 1:1 complex with salicylic acid. With rise in pH and concentration of salicylic acid, other complexes of 1:2 and 1:3 ratios, with respect to aluminium and salicylate, are formed.

FIG 7

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